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Coupling the FV and LBM codes

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1 Introduction

A complete analysis of the aero-mechanical behaviour of an helicopter rotor is an extremely complex task as it requires a proper description of the reciprocal interaction between the aerodynamic and mechanical behaviour of the rotating device. From a purely computational perspective, high fidelity simulations in this context require an iterative coupling between an high fidelity aerodynamic solver able to properly resolve the unsteady turbulent flow produced by the rotor itself and a structural code which accounts for the kinematics of the rotating device and how it is affected by the action of the aerodynamic forces exerted by the surrounding flow.

As concerns the aerodynamic part of the calculation, the intrinsically unsteady character of the Lattice Boltzmann Method (LBM), combined with its capability of treating complex geometries without the need of time-consuming meshing procedures, makes this approach an ideal candidate for treating this type of problems.

In recent research activities (e.g. in Ref. [2]), computational analysis of the aerodynamics of a full-scale helicopter rotor has been carried out via the commercial software PowerFlow. In this work, the advanced non-standard capabilities of PowerFlow are fully exploited: on the one side, the moving rotor is simulated via a multi-level mesh coupled with a Local Reference Frame approach[3], on the other side the high Mach flow expected near the rotor's blade tip is properly captured through the usage of a high order velocity discretization (D3Q39) of the Boltzmann Equation. Despite these advanced features and the complete analysis provided by the authors, this study does not include the mechanical behaviour of the rotor blades as a rigid-blade approach is employed.

In the following work we plan to couple the open-source code `waLBerla` to Leonardo's proprietary structural solvers to approach this kind of coupled aero-mechanical simulations. Despite advanced and highly optimized from a computational perspective, `waLBerla` does not offer the advanced capabilities provided by a commercial software like PowerFlow: in fact, this software package neither offers the possibility to solve the turbulent flow around rotating obstacles with uniform or non-uniform grids neither permits a correct description of high-Ma effects as these can not be properly captured through the currently implemented nearest-neighbor lattices, D3Q19 or D3Q27.

To overcome these concrete limitations, we decided to follow a different path to describe the fluid-dynamic component of these aero-mechanical simulations. The central idea is to represent the rotor blades by the forces they exert on the surrounding fluid instead of fully resolving their rotating solid surfaces. This approach, generally referred to as Actuator Surface Approach (ASA), enables a proper description of the rotor aerodynamics while guaranteeing a high computational speed-up w.r.t. fully resolved calculations.

The following document is organized as follow. In Section 2, we outline the general features of the ASA approach and we describe the implementation details of this methodology within `waLBerla` framework, with focus on the need of coupling the LB software with an external aeromechanic code to properly compute the forces appearing in the ASA method. Results obtained via the presented methodology have been already included in the submitted Deliverable D4.1 and will not be discussed in more detail in the following document. The presented implementation has been currently adopted for the simulation of the aerodynamics of rotating blades with externally imposed motion. We point out that the current code can be also directly exploited to couple the aerodynamics solution provided by `waLBerla` with a structural solver which would take as input the aerodynamic forces exerted on the blades and provide as output the induced mechanical displacements of the rotor components.

For future benchmarking and validation of `waLBerla` ASA results, we have also performed similar calculations using Fluent commercial solver. More precisely, in these simulations the aerodynamics is treated through a Reynolds Average Navier Stokes (RANS) approach (using a $k-\omega$ SST model for unresolved scales) in place of the LB stream-collide algorithm, while the presence of the rotating blades is included via Virtual-Blade-Model approach where physical rotor blades are replaced via momentum sources distributed across the computational cells in the circular region swept by the blades themselves, similarly to what is implemented in `waLBerla` for the ASA approach. This analysis is presented in Section 3, where preliminary results on the benchmark case of a Langley Rotor are compared with fully resolved 3D calculations performed via Fluent. The report is completed by Section 5, where the main conclusions and perspectives for future work are collected and discussed.

2 Implementation of the Actuator Surface Approach in waLBerla

The Actuator Surface Approach is a widely studied approach to represent rotating blades in fluid dynamics calculations. In the following we will provide a brief overview of the methodology: more details of this approach can be found in the vast available literature on the topic (see, for example, References [4] and [5] for applications of this approach to the modelling of wind turbine aerodynamics).

In this method, the individual blades are included in the fluid-dynamics momentum equations as an external volume-forcing term, representing the force exerted by the blade on the fluid itself during its motion. We point out that this approach is conceptually analogous to the Actuator Line Model, but the method here implemented adopts a different strategy to transfer the blade-exerted forces to the surrounding fluid.

In this approach, each blade is divided into sub-elements, each of them characterized by a constant transverse profile: for clarity in Figure 1a a schematic of the rotating blade (in anti-clockwise sense) is shown from the rotating axis point of view (here perpendicular to the plane), with the darker (lighter) blade representing the position at time $t + \delta t$ (t). Each square appearing on the rotating blade represents a sub-element in which the blade is subdivided, being the yellow dots the centers of each sub-element. In Figure 1b we present the transverse 2D-blade element profile, i.e. the model shape of each sub-element in the plane parallel to the axis of rotation.

Figure 1: (a) Schematic of a blade rotating around the axis perpendicular to the plane: the dark(light) area represents the blade at time $t + \delta t$ (t). Red triangles correspond to the areas swept by blade's sub-elements (gray squares) during a timestep. Yellow dots correspond to the centers of the sub-blade elements where velocity is sampled. (b) Example of the 2D transverse profile of each sub-blade element. Vertical green arrows correspond to the distributed loads, while the circle is the velocity evaluation point in mid-chord position.

At each iteration in the fluid solver (in this specific case the LBM) the fluid velocity is evaluated in correspondence of the yellow points in Figure 1a, corresponding to mid-chord position for the transverse profile of each blade element. As these points do not coincide with the nodes of the cartesian lattice and move with the rotating blade in time, the fluid velocity is not directly known at these positions. These quantities are evaluated through a trilinear interpolation method, using the velocities computed in the neighboring lattice nodes.

Once the velocity components are computed, the Reynolds number (Re), Mach number (Ma) and the effective angle of attack α seen by each blade element are determined and passed to the aeromechanical code for the evaluation of the sectional forces acting on the blade, using tabulated airfoil polar tables which provide lift and drag coefficients for different Mach and Re numbers at various angles of attack for the chosen 2D airfoil profile. These tables are available from experimental and/or 2D highly resolved CFD calculations and permit to compute the lift and drag forces via

$$f_{lift} = \frac{1}{2} \rho U_{local}^2 c C_L(Re, Ma, \alpha) \quad (1)$$

$$f_{drag} = \frac{1}{2} \rho U_{local}^2 c C_D(Re, Ma, \alpha) \quad (2)$$

being c the airfoil profile chord, ρ the fluid density and C_L and C_D the lift and drag coefficients taken from the available look up table for the specified angle of attack α and for the fluid relative velocity magnitude U_{local} .

For the implemented Actuator Surface Approach, it is assumed that the sectional load distribution is constant along the flat chord line and is depicted by the vertical green arrows in Figure 1b. We point out here that these sectional forces are the input to the structural solver to evaluate the mechanical response of the blade to the aerodynamic forces: therefore a fully coupled aero-structural simulation using these aerodynamic forces as inputs for the structural solver is straightforward with the current implementation and will be the topic of future work. In the present implementation, we assume the blade is rigid, i.e. we neglect the aero-induced elastic behaviour of the blade. These computed forces are finally transferred to the underlying fluid and are used in the forcing term of the LB equation in the successive iteration.

In order to account for the continuous blade motion during consecutive steps, aerodynamic loads are not only imposed at the respective blade positions at time $t + \delta t$. Instead, the distributed loads are applied on surfaces that are defined by the region that the blade sweeps between two time steps, as illustrated in Figure 1a. The swept area is approximated by triangular elements that are defined by the trailing edge position at the previous time step and the leading edge position at the current time step (see red triangles in Figure 1a) and it is computed by the aeromechanical code, which follow the blade motion. These load triangles feature a uniform distributed force corresponding to the loading on the blade elements spanning the corresponding area between successive timesteps.

To complete the algorithm, the force loads associated to each of this triangles is transferred to the computational LBM cartesian grid. In practice, for each cell in the computational domain we evaluate the intersection between the volume associated to the cubic cell and the load triangles. The force density in the LBM node \mathbf{x} is therefore computed as

$$\mathbf{f}(\mathbf{x}) = \sum_i \delta A_i(\mathbf{x}) \mathbf{f}_i \quad (3)$$

being δA_i the area of the i^{th} load triangle inside the cubic cell volume associated with the node \mathbf{x} and \mathbf{f}_i the uniform force carried by the triangle itself. The summation in Eq.3 is performed over all the load triangles intersecting this cell volume. A clarifying image representing this intersection area is presented in Figure 2a.

Figure 2: (a) Schematic of the triangle-voxel intersection (from Ref.[1]) to evaluate the area δA_i used in Equation 3 to compute the force density at node \mathbf{x} . (b) and (c) are representative for density distributions computed assuming no Gaussian smearing (b) and a finite Gaussian kernel smearing.

We point out that, differently from the conventional Actuator Line Model approach, the forces are not evaluated on a linear chain of points (each representing a blade element) and then directly spread on the underlying CFD lattice by a Gaussian smearing procedure. The followed approach prevents the possibility to have high forcing terms in individual cells of the LB grid which can cause severe issues in terms of both accuracy and numerical stability. To avoid numerical issues and to improve overall simulation fidelity, we have also implemented the possibility to combine the presented approach with the traditional Gaussian force-smearing procedure which further distributes forces over a region of user defined size. The on-lattice force densities for no Gaussian smearing and a finite Gaussian kernel smearing are respectively shown in Figure 2a and 2b. This last step completes the coupling cycle as these computed forces are finally included in the LBM stream-collide algorithm using an appropriate forcing scheme[6].

We point out that this coupling procedure is explicit in the sense that the evaluated blade loads are assumed to be constant throughout one timestep. Explicit coupling showed to be sufficient for the cases considered so far, as the chosen time step size was relatively small. It is however possible to extend the current implementation to an implicit treatment of the problem. This means that the computation of blade motion and aerodynamic loads is repeatedly carried out for one time step. In an iteration loop, the flow velocity field, blade loads and blade motion could be successively be updated using information from the current step until convergence has been reached.

Figure 3: Schematics of the coupling between waLBerla and the aero-mechanic code at the basis of the ASA method discussed in this section.

Figure 3 schematically represents the main steps followed in the ASA method discussed above and implemented via the coupling of waLBerla with an aeromechanic solver. The velocities and the load data (via the load triangles) are exchanged between waLBerla and the aeromechanic solver using TCP communication. Importantly, the current implementation fully exploits the MPI-based multi-GPU implementation of waLBerla to execute the most demanding numerical operations (i.e. the stream and collide steps). On the other side, both the calculation of force density fields starting from the aeromechanical loads and the velocity interpolation step are carried out on CPU as these operations involve only a small portion of the overall fluid nodes in the computational domain. Finally, to increase the accuracy of the simulation results, in particular the spatial sampling close to the blades where the smallest turbulent structures are expected, the proposed workflow has been used in combination with the block-based mesh-refinement strategy provided by waLBerla. As an example, in Figure 4 we display a slice of the instantaneous velocity field close to the blades (depicted as dashed black lines) with the multi-level mesh adopted in the calculation. We point out that the current implementation requires that the entire spatial region covered by the rotating blades must to be sampled with the same lattice spacing δx , i.e. no grid-level transitions should occur in this region.

Figure 4: Slice of the instantaneous velocity field around the rotating blades (depicted as black dashed lines) overlapped with the multi-level refined mesh used in the calculation. Notice that the region where the blades rotate is meshed with a single level of refinement.

2.1 Actuator Disc Demo Case

The project repository contains a simple simulation case to demonstrate the coupling sequence illustrated in Figure 3. In contrast to the treatment of individual rotor blades as described in Sections 2, a uniformly loaded rotor disc is modeled here, see Figure 5. This is particularly suited for illustration purposes, as blade motion does not need to be considered and an analytical solution for the induced velocity on the rotor disc exists for comparison. The Fortran source code for this actuator disc case is included in Section 2.1.1.

First, the simulation time step length and fluid properties are defined in lines 19–21. The Gaussian force distribution kernel, described in Section 2, is effectively disabled by setting a size of one in line 23. The computation grid setup, which comprises cell size, fluid domain size and grid refinement, is specified in lines 26–42. For the present case a constant static pressure is configured as boundary condition on all six sides of the box-shaped fluid domain (lines 44–

49). The transmission of the complete configuration to the `waLBerla` process running in parallel concludes the solver setup in line 53.

Lines 62 to 68 contain the actual simulation loop that iterates for a specified number of time steps. In contrast to this simple demonstration case, the number of time steps is typically not predefined when a full aeromechanics framework is coupled. Instead, the simulation is typically stopped once converged blade loads were detected using an appropriate criterion.

In each time step the current set of load triangles and evaluation points are passed to the `waLBerla` process, see line 63 and Section 2. After applying the distributed loads to the fluid, flow velocities at the specified evaluation points are returned from `waLBerla` in line 64. The flow velocities are usually taken into account for the evaluation of aerodynamic blade loads in the respective time step, see Section 2. As a rotor disc with constant loading is modeled in the present example case, the load triangles that represent this circular surface do not change during the simulation. They are thus computed once outside the simulation loop in line 58.

Furthermore, the flow velocities are evaluated only at the centre of the rotor disc, defined in line 60. In a simulation that considers individual blades, flow evaluation locations would move with the individual blades in order to take the local flow velocities into account for blade load computation. Here, the induced flow velocity at the rotor centre is printed in each time step, along with the analytical result from steady momentum theory.

Finally, a message with an empty list of evaluation point locations is sent to the `waLBerla` process in line 71 to signal the end of the coupled simulation.

Figure 5: Demonstration case with actuator disc (yellow) and a slice showing the instantaneous flow velocity field. The flow velocity evaluation point is located in the disc's centre (white dot).

2.1.1 Actuator Disc Demo Source Code

```

1 program actuator_disc_demo
2   use :: walberla_communicator
3   implicit none
4
5   double precision, parameter :: rotor_hub_position(3) = [0.0, 0.0, 0.01]
6   double precision, parameter :: rotor_radius = 5.0
7   double precision, parameter :: rotor_disc_loading = 500.0
8   integer, parameter :: number_of_time_steps = 1000
9   character(*), parameter :: output_directory = "output"
10
11  type(WalberlaSolverConfiguration) :: solver_configuration
12  type(WalberlaInput) :: solver_input
13  double precision, allocatable :: velocities(:, :)
14  double precision :: domain_edge_length
15  double precision :: steady_momentum_theory_induced_velocity
16  integer :: i
17
18
19  solver_configuration%time_step_length_seconds = 0.00034
20  solver_configuration%density = 1.225
21  solver_configuration%free_stream_velocity = [0.0, 0.0, 0.0]
22
23  solver_configuration%kernel_size = 1
24  solver_configuration%kernel_epsilon = 1.0
25
26  solver_configuration%cell_edge_length = 0.2
27  solver_configuration%minimum_corner_position = [0.0, 0.0, 0.0]
28  solver_configuration%number_of_blocks_x = 8
29  solver_configuration%number_of_blocks_y = 8
30  solver_configuration%number_of_blocks_z = 8
31  solver_configuration%cells_per_block_x = 16
32  solver_configuration%cells_per_block_y = 16
33  solver_configuration%cells_per_block_z = 16
34
35  domain_edge_length = solver_configuration%cell_edge_length* &
36    solver_configuration%number_of_blocks_x*solver_configuration%cells_per_block_x
37
38  solver_configuration%minimum_corner_position = &
39    [-0.5*domain_edge_length, -0.5*domain_edge_length, -0.5*domain_edge_length]
40
41  solver_configuration%refinement_region_minimum_corner_position = [-5.5, -5.5, -1.5]
42  solver_configuration%refinement_region_maximum_corner_position = [5.5, 5.5, 1.5]
43
44  solver_configuration%boundary_x_min = PressureBoundary
45  solver_configuration%boundary_x_max = PressureBoundary
46  solver_configuration%boundary_y_min = PressureBoundary
47  solver_configuration%boundary_y_max = PressureBoundary
48  solver_configuration%boundary_z_min = PressureBoundary
49  solver_configuration%boundary_z_max = PressureBoundary
50
51  solver_configuration%output_interval_steps = 1
52
53  call SendSolverConfiguration(solver_configuration, output_directory)
54
55
56  steady_momentum_theory_induced_velocity = sqrt(0.5*rotor_disc_loading/solver_configuration%density)
57
58  solver_input%load_triangles = GetActuatorDisc(rotor_hub_position, rotor_radius, rotor_disc_loading)
59
60  solver_input%evaluation_points = reshape(rotor_hub_position, [3, 1])
61
62  do i = 1, number_of_time_steps
63    call SendSolverInput(solver_input)
64    velocities = ReceiveFlowVelocities()
65
66    write (*, '(i4,a,f5.2,a,f5.2,a)') i, " Rotor induced velocity: ", velocities(3, 1), &
67      " m/s      Steady momentum theory result: ", steady_momentum_theory_induced_velocity, " m/s"
68  end do
69
70  solver_input%evaluation_points = reshape([double precision ::], [3, 0])
71  call SendSolverInput(solver_input)
72
73
74
75

```

```
76 contains
77
78 function GetActuatorDisc(rotor_hub_position, rotor_radius, rotor_disc_loading) result(load_triangles)
79     double precision, intent(in) :: rotor_hub_position(3)
80     double precision, intent(in) :: rotor_radius
81     double precision, intent(in) :: rotor_disc_loading
82     integer, parameter :: number_of_triangles = 72
83     double precision, parameter :: pi = 4.0*atan(1.0)
84     double precision, parameter :: circle_sector_angle = 2.0*pi/number_of_triangles
85     type(LoadTriangle) :: load_triangles(number_of_triangles)
86     integer :: i
87
88     do i = 1, number_of_triangles
89         load_triangles(i)%distributed_force = [double precision :: 0.0, 0.0, rotor_disc_loading]
90         load_triangles(i)%corners(:, 1) = rotor_hub_position
91         load_triangles(i)%corners(:, 2) = GetBladeTipPosition(rotor_hub_position, rotor_radius,
92             circle_sector_angle*(i - 1))
93         load_triangles(i)%corners(:, 3) = GetBladeTipPosition(rotor_hub_position, rotor_radius,
94             circle_sector_angle*i)
95     end do
96
97 end function GetActuatorDisc
98
99 function GetBladeTipPosition(rotor_hub_position, rotor_radius, blade_angle_rad) result(tip_position)
100     double precision, intent(in) :: rotor_hub_position(3)
101     double precision, intent(in) :: rotor_radius
102     double precision, intent(in) :: blade_angle_rad
103     double precision :: tip_position(3)
104
105     tip_position = [rotor_hub_position(1) + cos(blade_angle_rad)*rotor_radius, &
106         rotor_hub_position(2) + sin(blade_angle_rad)*rotor_radius, &
107         rotor_hub_position(3)]
108
109 end function GetBladeTipPosition
110
111 end program
```

3 Coupling FV with an Aeromechanical Solver

3.1 Introduction

In order to gradually approach the challenge of coupling Ansys Fluent to a structural dynamics solver, it was chosen to begin simulating a simple hover case, adopting different methodologies. This initial step provided a foundational understanding of the computational requirements involved.

Several CFD modeling approaches were tested, including fully resolved 3D blade simulations with the Multiple Reference Frame (MRF) method and the Virtual Blade Model (VBM). The primary goal of these evaluations was to assess the computational cost of each method, with accuracy as a secondary consideration, to determine their feasibility for coupling with a structural dynamics solver. Based on these analyses, it was evident that simplified methods were necessary to maintain computational efficiency while enabling external tool integration.

The need to target unsteady simulations led to the exclusion of the VBM approach. Although VBM is computationally efficient, its stationary nature makes it unsuitable for unsteady coupling scenarios. Instead, we adopted an unsteady actuator disk-based simplification, which retains the CFD solver's capability to model wake structures accurately. This approach leverages a coupling between the mid-fidelity aerodynamic module of Leonardo Aeromechanical Solver, an internally developed unsteady aerodynamic solver, and Fluent. This module offers the additional advantage of being natively integrated with the Aeromechanical Solver, an internally developed aeroelastic code, facilitating future expansions of the coupling framework.

The developed dual-solver hybrid method [7] is capable of providing accurate results without incurring the prohibitive computational costs of single-solver unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (uRANS) methods. Hybrid approaches like this effectively bridge the gap between lower-fidelity design methods and high-fidelity CFD methods, such as fully blade-resolved uRANS simulations, which, while capable of capturing complex aerodynamic phenomena, remain computationally expensive and resource-intensive.

The initial implementation involved steady-state coupling between the mid fidelity aerodynamic module of Leonardo Aeromechanical Solver and Fluent as a stepping stone toward the more complex unsteady coupling. This gradual progression ensured robust integration and allowed for the validation of intermediate steps. Subsequently, the framework was extended to unsteady Leonardo Solver-Fluent coupling, laying the groundwork for structural coupling with Leonardo Aeromechanical Solver.

This structured methodology reflects a balance between computational efficiency and physical accuracy, enabling seamless integration into a unified aero-structural simulation framework.

3.2 Full 3D CFD Simulation of the Rotor

The initial simulation methodology explored involved a fully resolved three-dimensional Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD) simulation conducted in Fluent. This approach serves both as a validation case and as a foundational framework for future coupling with an aero-mechanical solver. Within this coupling framework, Fluent directly computes aerodynamic loads by integrating the pressure distribution over the blade surface. The interface structure, detailed in Section 3.4, can be flexibly adapted by modifying the data exchange configuration, further enhancing the accuracy and fidelity of the simulation.

Full 3D CFD simulations offer a high-fidelity representation of rotor aerodynamics by solving the Navier-Stokes equations directly around the blades. Unlike the other approaches investigated, this method resolves the detailed flow field without relying on simplified models like the Virtual Blade Model (VBM) or Unsteady Actuator Disk. It inherently captures the unsteady, three-dimensional flow characteristics, including blade-vortex interactions, wake dynamics, and stall behavior.

However, these benefits are offset by significantly higher computational costs compared to the simplified methods analyzed in this study. When coupling these CFD approaches with an aero-mechanical solver, it becomes crucial to strike a balance between computational efficiency and the seamless integration of external tools. This necessity underscores the importance of exploring alternative simplified models.

Test Case. For this development, the Langley rotor was chosen as the case study. It is a two-bladed rotor featuring straight, untwisted blades with a constant chord length, designed with NACA0012 airfoil sections. The choice of the Langley rotor is due to its well-documented experimental data, which facilitates validation of the computational methods. The primary characteristics and specifications of the Langley rotor are detailed in [8]. Using the available experimental data, we performed a series of simulations for the Langley rotor in hover conditions, systematically varying the collective pitch of the blades. The parameters used for these simulations are summarized in 1.

These simulations replicate those conducted with other methodologies, providing an independent and detailed assessment of rotor performance while serving as a benchmark for evaluating the trade-offs between computational

Collective Pitch Blade [deg]
3
4.5
6.7
8.5
9.2

Table 1: Simulations Collective Pitch blade angles.

efficiency and prediction accuracy. The Moving Reference Frame (MRF) technique was employed to model the rotational motion of the blades. MRF assumes a steady-state solution in a rotating reference frame, simplifying the simulation of rotating systems. Periodic boundary conditions were applied to exploit the symmetry of the two-bladed rotor system, modeling only half of the domain to reduce computational expense.

Mesh generation was a critical step in the setup of this simulation, as the accuracy and stability of the results depend significantly on the quality and resolution of the mesh. The starting point for mesh generation was the rotor blade geometry. A surface mesh with a high refinement level was created to resolve the leading and trailing edges accurately. This refinement is essential to capture boundary layer effects and to predict flow separation and reattachment along the blade surface.

Figure 6: Blade Surface Mesh

To accurately resolve the boundary layer and capture flow details near the blade, multiple layers of cells were generated around the blade surface. The number of layers and their thickness were chosen to ensure a sufficient wall-normal resolution, meeting the requirements for turbulence modeling, typically with a dimensionless wall distance (y^+) less than 1 for the $k - \omega$ SST model used.

Figure 7: Blade Boundary Layer

An inner semi-cylindrical domain was created to contain the rotor blades. This region was meshed using polyhedral cells with refinement towards the blade surface to maintain high resolution in the vicinity of the blades. Polyhedral cells offer better convergence and flexibility in capturing complex geometries compared to tetrahedral cells.

To facilitate the application of the MRF technique, interfaces were created between the inner cylinder and the surrounding domain. These interfaces allow the rotational motion in the MRF region to interact with the stationary outer domain seamlessly.

Figure 8: 3D Inner Cylinder Mesh

The external domain was modeled as a structured semi-cylinder, with refinement levels gradually decreasing away from the rotor to minimize computational costs while maintaining accuracy in regions influenced by the rotor wake. The outer boundary conditions were set far enough from the rotor to avoid reflections and ensure an undisturbed free-stream flow. The resulting mesh consists of a total of 12 million cells.

The turbulence model used for this simulation was the $k - \omega$ SST model. The solver employed a coupled pressure-velocity approach, with pseudo-transient stabilization to enhance convergence. Boundary conditions included periodic boundaries to model the symmetric half-domain and a no-slip condition on the blade surfaces. The inlet and outlet boundaries were specified as pressure inlet and outlet conditions, respectively. Gravity effects were neglected, consistent with the hover condition described in following Sections.

3.2.1 Results

Figure 9: Component Z Velocity contours (y-z plane at x=0) at collective 6.7°

The results obtained from these simulations are presented and analyzed in detail in Section 4.

3.3 Virtual Blade Model - VBM

The Virtual Blade Model (VBM) is a widely utilized technique in rotorcraft aerodynamics for simulating lifting rotors within a flow field analyzed through finite volume methods. This method replaces the physical rotor blades with momentum sources distributed across the cell region swept by the blades. These momentum sources are computed using Blade Element Theory (BET), with the aid of lift and drag coefficients lookup tables to estimate rotor forces.

VBM effectively captures time-averaged aerodynamic effects, such as rotor performance, fuselage drag within the rotor wake, and approximate rotor-airframe interactions. However, it is not designed to simulate unsteady blade dynamics, which require more advanced modeling approaches. Despite this limitation, VBM provides a computationally efficient tool for analyzing the overall aerodynamic behavior of rotorcraft.

In the following, we will not go in the details of this approach but we refer the interested reader to Wahono PhD thesis [9] for a deeper explanation of the adopted implementation.

The VBM cannot fully simulate the unsteady, highly three-dimensional flow around the rotor. Furthermore, the limitations of the method render it unsuitable for coupling with dynamic solvers that operate in a time-marching framework. Dynamic solvers require induced velocities to be computed at each time step, which is incompatible with the inherently steady-state nature of VBM.

The same series of simulations was performed using this method, implemented through user-defined functions, across all previously studied conditions to establish a baseline for evaluating the trade-offs between computational efficiency and prediction accuracy. This assessment enables a direct comparison of the three methodologies analyzed for their suitability in coupling with an aero-mechanic solver. It is important to note that the VBM, known for its seamless integration with RANS-based flow solvers and reliability in time-averaged predictions, serves as a valid reference for comparison in this specific hovering test case.

The test case utilized for the Virtual Blade Model (VBM) simulations corresponds to the Langley rotor [8]. The rotor was tested under hover conditions with an imposed collective pitch angle, as described earlier. Simulations were conducted for a range of collective pitch blade angles, as detailed in Table 1, using LHD UDF.

To simulate this configuration, two distinct mesh components were created. The first component was a cylindrical region enclosing the rotor disc, discretized with approximately 8000 faces. This mesh was unstructured to accommodate the complex geometry of the rotor. The second component was an external cylinder with a diameter of approximately 70 m and a length of about 280 m, with the rotor hub positioned at its center. This external mesh featured varying levels of refinement and was generated using Fluent's hexcore Cartesian meshing tool. A layer of pyramidal elements was created between the inner and outer cylinders.

Figure 10: Rotor Mesh

Figure 11: External Mesh for VBM test cases

The mesh details are summarized in Table 2:

The solver setup employed a coupled pressure-velocity approach, utilizing the pseudo-transient method to enhance numerical stability and improve convergence rates. The turbulence model, as well as the operating and boundary conditions, were configured as described in detail in Section 3.6.

Mesh Component	Type	Size (Millions of Cells)
Component Mesh	Unstructured	0.2
External Mesh	Unstructured	4

Table 2: Mesh details for VBM simulations.

3.3.1 Results

Figure 12: Static Pressure contours (y-z plane at x=0) at collective 6.7°

Figure 13: Component Z Velocity contours (y-z plane at x=0) at collective 6.7°

The results obtained from these simulations are presented and analyzed in detail in Section 4.

3.4 Coupling Methodology

This section presents an implementation similar to that discussed in Section 2, where the approach was applied within the waLBerla framework. This methodology employs the mid-fidelity aerodynamic module of Leonardo's Aeromechanical Solver to simulate blade aerodynamics, utilizing its detailed physical representation of rotor blades and seamless integration capabilities within an aeromechanical solver, while Fluent resolves the near-body flow field around the rotorcraft with a finite volume modeling while representing the rotor through an Unsteady Actuator Disk approach.

By dividing the computational tasks, this framework achieves not only computational efficiency but also seamless integration with external tools. Furthermore, it allows the simulation to incorporate complex flow environments, such as those involving ship wakes. Initially, blade loads of a rotor in clean air are computed using the mid-fidelity aerodynamic module of Leonardo Aeromechanical Solver or any suitable tool. These loads are then passed to Fluent, where they are implemented as momentum sources, enabling Fluent to calculate the inflow under the given conditions while accounting for interactions with the complex flow field. This inflow data is subsequently fed back to the mid-fidelity aerodynamic solver, which uses a Blade Element Theory (BET) approach to calculate updated blade loads, which will

take into account the inflow resulting from the interaction of rotor load and external flow field.

This iterative exchange facilitates accurate evaluation of aerodynamic loads that would otherwise be difficult to compute using Fluent alone. Additionally, with its native compatibility with structural solvers, this framework is inherently designed for coupling with an aeromechanical solver, enabling further extensions for fully coupled simulations.

The interface developed and documented in the code repository to couple these two solvers will also serve as the foundation for coupling with a dynamic solver capable of simultaneously resolving rotor motion and aerodynamics, as illustrated in Figure 14. This evolution will enable the analysis of fully coupled aero-mechanical phenomena, advancing the state of rotorcraft aerodynamic and structural modeling.

Figure 14: Schematics of the coupling between FLUENT and the aero-mechanic code simultaneously resolving rotor motion and aerodynamics.

The reported coupling methodology is based on the dual-solver approach developed. As illustrated in the flowchart in Figure 15, this framework integrates an aero-mechanical solver which, under externally imposed motion, focuses solely on resolving the aerodynamics of the rotor blade. For this purpose, the mid-fidelity aerodynamic module of Leonardo Aeromechanical Solver proved to be a suitable choice.

To initialize the coupling loop at iteration zero, momentum sources must be assigned to the rotor disk in Fluent. This process begins with a mid-fidelity simulation utilizing the native wake model within the aerodynamic module of Leonardo's Solver, wherein the rotor blade is divided into sub-elements and analyzed using lifting-line theory. The sectional aerodynamic coefficients—lift, drag, and pitching moment—are defined as functions of local parameters such as angle of attack, Mach number, Reynolds number, and, if applicable, control surface deflections. The circulation of the lifting line is calculated by solving a non-linear system that links circulation with tabulated aerodynamic coefficients for each lifting section. These aerodynamic coefficients are typically supplied through C81 ASCII files. In the specific case of hover, aerodynamic loads are computed over an entire rotor revolution, ensuring high-fidelity evaluation of integral forces. It is worth noting that the initialization of the coupling loop could have been accomplished

using any tool capable of generating rotor disk momentum sources, not exclusively the mid-fidelity aerodynamic module of Leonardo Aeromechanical Solver.

Figure 15: Schematics of the coupling between Fluent and the aero-mechanic code with externally imposed motion

Using this method, the sectional load distribution along the rotor blade is calculated. Before these loads are transferred to the finite volume (FV) solver, the momentum sources are derived from the spanwise load distribution obtained via the aero-mechanical solver. Specifically, this coupling approach substitutes the physical rotor blades in the CFD simulation with distributed momentum sources within the cell region swept by the blades. The momentum source method employed [10] introduces additional source terms into the CFD solver's momentum equations, effectively simulating the aerodynamic forces generated by the rotor and accurately capturing rotor-induced flow effects.

At each iteration of the fluid solver (in this case, Fluent), the fluid velocity is passed to the aero-mechanical solver to compute the sectional forces acting on the blade using a Blade Element Theory (BET) model (Figures 14 15). These sectional forces serve as inputs for a structural solver to evaluate the mechanical response of the blade to aerodynamic forces. Therefore, a fully coupled aero-structural simulation, using these aerodynamic forces as inputs for the structural solver, can be straightforwardly implemented with the current framework and will be explored in future work. In the present study, however, the blade is assumed to be rigid, neglecting any aero-elastic behavior.

To account for the continuous blade motion over consecutive time steps, aerodynamic loads are not only applied at the blade's positions at $t + \delta t$, but are distributed over the regions swept by the blade between two time steps. The same approach described in Section 2 can be adopted here. Without evaluating the intersection between the cell volume and the load triangles, momentum sources are generated from the load distribution and used as input profiles in Fluent by considering the evaluation points' positions.

This coupling procedure is explicit, as the blade loads are assumed constant throughout each time step. Explicit coupling has been sufficient for the cases studied, given the relatively small time step sizes chosen. Nevertheless, the current implementation can be extended to implicit coupling, where blade motion and aerodynamic loads are

computed iteratively within each time step. In such an iterative loop, the flow velocity field, blade loads, and blade motion would be updated successively until convergence is achieved (as in Figure 14).

Figure 15 schematically represents the main steps of the dual-solver approach discussed above. Data exchange between Fluent and the aero-mechanical solver, including velocities and load data, is managed through TCP communication, ensuring seamless integration and accurate coupling.

In the steady-state scenario, Fluent and the mid-fidelity aerodynamic module of Leonardo Aeromechanical Solver were coupled to test and validate the data exchange mechanism and establish operational synchronization. While steady-state simulations do not fully replicate unsteady physical phenomena, they form a critical foundation for verifying the solvers' interoperability, enabling a smooth transition to dynamic analyses.

Following the successful integration in steady-state conditions, the simulation framework progresses to unsteady-state scenarios, where the coupled solvers interact iteratively at each time step. This dynamic coupling loop allows for continuous updates and real-time adaptation of aerodynamic data between Fluent and the Leonardo mid-fidelity aerodynamic solver, thereby improving the accuracy and fidelity of the simulation in transient conditions. Additionally, the framework facilitates seamless implementation of the structural analysis component using the Leonardo Aeromechanical Solver, further broadening its applicability.

Future applications of this dual-solver methodology will target more intricate scenarios, including interactions between multiple rotors and rotorcraft operating in complex environments, such as ship operations. These advanced cases, which involve wake interactions and detailed blade-resolved calculations, are currently infeasible using standalone CFD due to excessive computational demands. The dual-solver framework, validated through these simulations, aims to expand the capabilities of current computational methods, enabling efficient and accurate analysis of complex rotorcraft dynamics while managing computational costs effectively.

3.4.1 Implementation

Steady-State. In this study case, we start with a mid-fidelity aerodynamic simulation to evaluate the loads needed by Fluent. The simulation done to evaluate the loads used a Part 1D model in the Body module, based on the lifting line theory. The lifting line theory simplifies the complex aerodynamic interactions of a wing or rotor blade by modeling it as a line of bound vortices, facilitating the calculation of lift distribution along the span. This simulation also incorporates a numerical wake to the wake dynamics effectively and better estimates of lift, drag, and moments. The Vortex Ring Wake model was employed as the numerical wake representation.

From this simulation, we obtain the integral loads and the loads per unit length for each section of the blade and for each time-step (azimuth discretization). In the stationary case, we spread the force across the whole disk, using the equivalence between time averaging and geometric averaging, which is valid at constant rotation speed. For unsteady cases, though, it's different—we calculate momentum sources based only on the circular sector covered by the blade as it sweeps through, giving us more precise results. Using the mid-fidelity aerodynamic solver outputs and interpolating them on the computational grid, we calculate the momentum source (steady state case) using the following formula:

$$\Delta q \left[\frac{N}{m^3} \right] = \frac{\Delta T}{\Delta r} \frac{N_b}{2\pi r H}$$

Where:

- ΔT [N] is the thrust of the local element,
- N_b is the number of blades,
- H height of the disk in the mesh,
- r is the local radius,
- Δr is the radial length of the local element.

The loads computed by the wake solver (Leonardo mid-fidelity aerodynamic solver) are seamlessly integrated into the near-body unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (uRANS) solution in Fluent. These loads are incorporated as a momentum source profile within a one-layer-thick computational mesh that represents the rotor's rotating surface. Although the rotor surface is modeled as a disk, it is assigned a finite (albeit small) thickness, ensuring it has a defined volume for accurate numerical representation. The method is based on the assumption that any force on the blade (in each space direction) can be seen as a source of momentum and can be applied locally.

From the CFD simulation, we obtain the rotorcraft inflow using PyFluent tools, which serves as the input for the subsequent mid-fidelity simulation. This simulation utilizes a Part 1D model without any wake, effectively creating

a Blade Element Theory (BET) model of the blade. The BET model decomposes the blade into smaller elements, calculating the aerodynamic forces and moments on each element based on local flow conditions, providing detailed insight into blade performance.

The solvers exchange output and input data via TCP communication, facilitating the transfer of momentum sources and inflow data to the Leonardo mid-fidelity aerodynamic Solver, as demonstrated in the example described earlier. Currently, Fluent receives the momentum sources as a profile file. This method is employed because, at the present stage of `pyfluent` development, it is the only available means to input momentum sources into a Fluent session. These profiles are generated based on output forces provided by the mid-fidelity aerodynamic solver or any compatible aeromechanical solver. In contrast, the inflow data is transmitted through a dedicated communication interface between the two solvers, ensuring seamless integration and synchronization.

Unsteady-State. The unsteady simulation was conducted for the same cases as the steady-state analysis, as detailed in Table 1. The coupling approach remains fundamentally similar in principle. However, key adjustments were made to the data exchange frequency between the software tools and the definition of the momentum sources.

The initial mid-fidelity aerodynamic simulation mirrors the setup used in the steady-state coupling. However, in the unsteady case the coupling proceeds in a time-accurate manner. Specifically, after each azimuthal sector swept by the rotor blades during one time step, the load distribution over that sector is transferred.

Using the output from the mid-fidelity aerodynamic solver, interpolated onto the computational grid, the unsteady momentum sources are calculated based on the following expression:

$$\Delta q \left[\frac{N}{m^3} \right] = \frac{\Delta T}{\Delta r} \frac{N_{azimuth}}{2\pi r H}$$

Where:

- ΔT [N] is the thrust generated by the local blade element,
- $N_{azimuth}$ is the azimuthal angle covered by the blade in one time step, representing the discretized rotor motion for unsteady analysis,
- H height of the disk in the mesh,
- r is the radial position of the element,
- Δr is the radial span of the local blade element.

The inflow for the rotor is subsequently obtained from the CFD simulation using PyFluent tools. This inflow serves as the input for the next mid-fidelity aerodynamic simulation time-step.

3.5 Fluent Communication Demo Case

The project repository contains a simple simulation case to demonstrate the coupling between an aeromechanics framework and the Fluent solver. A two-bladed rotor is modeled here, with distributed line loads that are proportional to the radial position on each blade. The Fortran source code for this actuator disc case is included in Section 3.5.1.

It is assumed here that the simulation configuration, such as time step length and computational grid, are configured within the Fluent solver process running in parallel. Lines 24 to 45 contain the actual simulation loop that iterates for a specified number of time steps. In contrast to this simple demonstration case, the number of time steps is typically not predefined when a full aeromechanics framework is coupled. Instead, the simulation is stopped once converged blade loads were detected using an appropriate criterion.

In each time step a load line is computed for each blade in lines 28–31. The placement is based on the current rotor angle and the blade spacing. Sectional blade lift is assumed to depend linearly on the radial station, reaching a specified distributed force value at the tip.

Flow velocity evaluation points are placed at the midpoints between adjacent nodes of the load lines, see source code line 33. The solver input for the respective time step, comprising load lines and evaluation points, is sent to the Fluent process in line 35. After applying the distributed loads to the fluid, flow velocities at the specified evaluation points are returned from Fluent in line 37. The flow velocities are usually taken into account for the evaluation of aerodynamic blade loads in the respective time step. As constant loads are assumed here for the revolving blades, the resulting flow velocities are just printed and not processed further.

Finally, a message with an empty list of evaluation point locations is sent to the Fluent process in line 50 to signal the end of the coupled simulation.

3.5.1 Fluent Communication Demo Source Code

```

1 program demo_framework
2   use :: fluent_communicator
3   implicit none
4
5   type(FluentInput) :: solver_input
6   type(FluentOutput) :: solver_output
7   integer :: i, j
8   real :: blade_angle
9   real :: pi = 4.0*atan(1.0)
10
11  real :: rotor_rotational_speed = -65.573770492
12  real, allocatable :: blade_radial_stations(:)
13  integer :: number_of_blades = 2
14
15  real :: time_step_length = 0.001
16  integer :: number_of_time_steps = 2
17
18  blade_radial_stations = [0.4763, 0.5686, 0.6610, 0.7534, 0.8458, 0.9382, 1.0306, 1.1230, &
19                        1.2154, 1.3078, 1.4002, 1.4926, 1.5850, 1.6774, 1.7697, 1.8621, &
20                        1.9545, 2.0469, 2.1393, 2.2317, 2.3241]
21
22  allocate (solver_input%load_lines(number_of_blades))
23
24  do i = 1, number_of_time_steps
25    write (*, *)
26    write (*, *) "Time Step", i
27
28    do j = 1, number_of_blades
29      blade_angle = rotor_rotational_speed*time_step_length*(i - 1) + (j - 1)*2.0*pi/number_of_blades
30      solver_input%load_lines(j) = GetBladeLoadLine(blade_angle, blade_radial_stations)
31    end do
32
33    solver_input%evaluation_points = GetEvaluationPoints(solver_input%load_lines)
34
35    call SendSolverInput(solver_input)
36
37    solver_output = ReceiveSolverOutput()
38
39    write (*, *) "Received Evaluation Data:"
40    do j = 1, size(solver_output%evaluation_data)
41      write (*, '(i2, a, (f10.3), a, *(f10.3))') j, &
42          " Air Density ", solver_output%evaluation_data(j)%air_density, &
43          " Velocity ", solver_output%evaluation_data(j)%flow_velocity
44    end do
45  end do
46
47  ! send solver input with empty evaluation points to signal end of simulation
48  solver_input%evaluation_points = reshape([double precision ::], [3, 0])
49
50  call SendSolverInput(solver_input)
51
52 contains
53
54  function GetBladeLoadLine(blade_angle, radial_stations) result(load_line)
55    real :: blade_angle
56    real :: radial_stations(:)
57    type(LoadLine) :: load_line
58    integer :: i
59
60    real :: tip_distributed_force = -1000.0
61
62    allocate (load_line%load_nodes(size(radial_stations)))
63
64    do i = 1, size(radial_stations)
65      load_line%load_nodes(i)%position = &
66          [cos(blade_angle)*radial_stations(i), sin(blade_angle)*radial_stations(i), 0.0]
67      load_line%load_nodes(i)%distributed_force = &
68          [0.0, 0.0, tip_distributed_force*radial_stations(i)/radial_stations(size(radial_stations))]
69    end do
70
71  end function GetBladeLoadLine
72
73  function GetEvaluationPoints(load_lines) result(evaluation_points)
74    type(LoadLine) :: load_lines(:)
75    double precision, allocatable :: evaluation_points(:, :)

```

```

76     integer :: i, j
77
78     allocate (evaluation_points(3, 0))
79
80     do i = 1, size(load_lines)
81         do j = 1, (size(load_lines(i)%load_nodes) - 1)
82             evaluation_points = reshape([evaluation_points, &
83                 0.5*(load_lines(i)%load_nodes(j)%position + load_lines(i)%load_nodes(j + 1)%position)], &
84                 [3, size(evaluation_points, 2) + 1])
85         end do
86     end do
87
88     end function GetEvaluationPoints
89
90 end program

```

3.5.2 Python Interface Code

The launch of the Fluent session and the configuration of the Fluent setup for the coupling are performed using the `pyfluent` library, as reported in the Python interface code below (lines 29–141). In each time step the current set of loads distribution and evaluation points are passed to the Fluent process (line 148). After computing the momentum source (lines 148–239), and applying them to the fluid (lines 241–255), flow velocities at the specified evaluation points are returned from Fluent (lines 257–293). The flow velocities are usually taken into account for the evaluation of aerodynamic blade loads in the respective time step. Finally, a message with an empty list of evaluation point locations is sent to the Fluent process to signal the end of the coupled simulation.

Ansys Fluent and PyFluent Integration. Ansys Fluent is widely recognized for its robust capabilities in solving complex fluid flow problems and its versatility across diverse engineering applications. To further enhance its functionality, PyFluent provides a Python-based interface that integrates seamlessly with Fluent, enabling programmatic control over simulation setup, execution, and post-processing. This integration was instrumental in developing the interface used to manage and control the Fluent session, as illustrated in 3.5.2.

The Python component of the code, documented in the project repository, includes a simple simulation case that demonstrates the coupling sequence. This framework is designed to be user-customizable, allowing for the execution of various types of Fluent simulations—ranging from fully resolved blade models to the implementation of the Unsteady Actuator Disk for the dual-solver approach described in this study.

The PyFluent interface leverages a client-server architecture built on Google remote procedure calls (gRPC), allowing users to interact with Fluent entirely through Python. This enables the automation of workflows and supports hybrid computational approaches. PyFluent extends Fluent’s capabilities by enabling advanced customization, such as scripting meshing operations, managing solver sessions, retrieving field data as `numpy` arrays, and performing post-processing with Python libraries like `matplotlib`. While PyFluent significantly enhances productivity and flexibility, it operates within the same licensing framework as a standard Fluent simulation. This ensures compliance with Ansys licensing terms while enabling accurate, efficient, and customizable CFD simulations tailored to a wide range of engineering challenges.

```

1 import fluent_communicator
2 import numpy as np
3 from array import array
4 import matplotlib.pyplot as plt
5 from ctypes import c_double
6 from scipy.interpolate import griddata
7 from mpl_toolkits.mplot3d import Axes3D
8 import zipfile
9 import sys
10 import os
11 import ansys.fluent.core as pyfluent
12
13 def get_row(matrix, row_idx):
14     return [column[row_idx] for column in matrix]
15
16 N_BLADE = 2
17 OMEGA = 65.05
18 R = 2.324
19 H = 0.04
20 ALPHA_ROT = 0.0
21 BETA_ROT = 0.0
22 BETA_ROT_WIND = 0.0
23 CENTER = [0.0, 0.0, 0.0]
24 ROTATION_DIRECTION = 0
25 WIND_DIRECTION = 0
26 N_AZIMUTH_AERO = 2

```

```
27
28
29 solver = pyfluent.launch_fluent(
30     precision="double",
31     version="3d",
32     mode="solver",
33     cleanup_on_exit=True,
34     start_transcript=True,
35     ui_mode="gui",
36     additional_arguments= "-pib.ofed -mpi=openmpi"
37     #,py=True
38 )
39
40 tui = solver.tui
41 solver.file.start_transcript(file_name = "/archive/elicotteri_aerodinamica_share/Multixscale_A_F/fluent_copy/
42     HOVER_test/Fluent.log")
43
44 #--- READ MESH ---
45
46 solver.file.read_case(file_name='/archive/elicotteri_aerodinamica/USERS/ssiciliani/Langley_rotor/MESH_GENERATION/
47     AD_MESH_NEW.msh.h5')
48
49 #--- IMPLEMENTED MODEL ---
50
51 solver.setup.models.viscous={
52     "model" : "k-omega",
53     "k_omega_model" : "sst"
54 }
55
56 solver.setup.models.energy = {
57     "enabled" : True,
58     "inlet_diffusion" : True,
59     "viscous_dissipation" : True
60 }
61
62 #--- MATERIAL USED ---
63
64 air = solver.setup.materials.fluid["air"]
65 air.density.option = "ideal-gas"
66 air.viscosity.option = "sutherland"
67 air.viscosity.sutherland={
68     "option" : "three-coefficient-method",
69     "reference_viscosity" : 1.716e-05,
70     "reference_temperature" : 273.15,
71     "effective_temperature" : 110.56
72 }
73
74 #--- OPERATING CONDITIONS ---
75
76 solver.setup.general.operating_conditions.gravity.enable=False
77 solver.setup.general.operating_conditions = {
78     "reference_pressure_location" : [0, 0, 50],
79     "operating_pressure" : 101325,
80     "reference_pressure_method" : 'Connected and disconnected fluid zones'
81 }
82
83 #--- BOUNDARY CONDITIONS TYPE ---
84
85 solver.setup.boundary_conditions.pressure_inlet['bb_inlet_zpos'] = {
86     'momentum': {
87         "gauge_total_pressure" : {'option': 'value', 'value': 0.1531} #inserire pressione dinamica in Pa! 0.5m/s
88     },
89     'turbulence': {
90         'turbulent_specification': 'K and Omega',
91         'turbulent_kinetic_energy': {'option': 'value', 'value': 1.0},
92         'specific_dissipation_rate': {'option': 'value', 'value': 1.0}
93     },
94     'thermal': {'t0': {'option': 'value', 'value': 288.15}}
95 }
96
97 solver.setup.boundary_conditions.pressure_outlet['bb_outlet_zneg'] = {
98     'turbulence': {
99         'turbulent_specification': 'K and Omega',
100         'turbulent_kinetic_energy': {'option': 'value', 'value': 1.0},
101         'specific_dissipation_rate': {'option': 'value', 'value': 1.0}
102     },
103     'thermal': {'t0': {'option': 'value', 'value': 288.15}}
104 }
105
106 solver.setup.reference_values.compute(from_zone_type = "pressure-inlet", from_zone_name = "bb_inlet_zpos", phase =
107     "mixture")
108
109
110
```

```

100 #--- GRADIENT SCHEME ---
101 solver.solution.methods.gradient_scheme = "green-gauss-node-based"
102 solver.solution.methods.warped_face_gradient_correction.enable=False
103
104 #--- SOLUTION CONTROL ---
105 solver.setup.general.solver.time = "unsteady-1st-order"
106 solver.solution.methods.p_v_coupling.flow_scheme = "PISO"
107
108 solver.solution.controls.limits = {
109     'min_pressure': 2000.0,
110     'max_pressure': 200000.0,
111     'min_temperature': 10.0,
112     'max_temperature': 500.0,
113     'min_tke': 1e-14,
114     'min_omega': 1e-20,
115     'max_turb_visc_ratio': 10000000.0
116 }
117
118 #--- MONITORING ---
119 solver.setup.reference_values.area = 1.000
120 solver.setup.reference_values.length = 1.000
121
122 solver.solution.monitor.residual.equations['*'].monitor = True
123 solver.solution.monitor.residual.equations['*'].check_convergence = False
124
125
126 #--- INITIALIZATION ---
127 solver.solution.initialization.compute_defaults(from_zone_type='pressure-inlet', from_zone_name='bb_inlet_zpos')
128 solver.solution.initialization.hybrid_initialize()
129
130 #--- RUN ---
131
132 solver.solution.run_calculation.transient_controls.type = ("Fixed")
133 solver.solution.run_calculation.transient_controls.method = ("User-Specified")
134 solver.solution.run_calculation.reporting_interval = 1
135 solver.solution.run_calculation.profile_update_interval = 1
136 solver.solution.run_calculation.transient_controls.max_iter_per_time_step = 100
137 solver.solution.run_calculation.transient_controls.extrapolate_variables = True
138 solver.solution.run_calculation.transient_controls.time_step_count = 1
139 solver.solution.run_calculation.transient_controls.time_step_size = 2* np.pi / (N_AZIMUTH_AERO * OMEGA)
140 solver.solution.run_calculation.transient_controls.max_iter_per_time_step = 100
141 solver.solution.controls.under_relaxation = {'body-force': 1.0, 'density': 1, 'k': 0.8, 'mom': 0.7, 'omega': 0.8,
142     'pressure': 0.3, 'temperature': 1.0, 'turb-viscosity': 1}
143
144 time_step = 0
145
146 while True:
147     time_step += 1
148
149     input = fluent_communicator.ReceiveSolverInput()
150
151     # an empty array of evaluation points signals end of simulation
152     if len(input.evaluation_points) == 0:
153         break
154
155     print("\nTime Step", time_step)
156
157     Fx = np.empty((len(input.load_lines[1].load_nodes), len(input.load_lines)))
158     Fy = np.empty((len(input.load_lines[1].load_nodes), len(input.load_lines)))
159     Fz = np.empty((len(input.load_lines[1].load_nodes), len(input.load_lines)))
160     x = np.empty((len(input.load_lines[1].load_nodes), len(input.load_lines)))
161     y = np.empty((len(input.load_lines[1].load_nodes), len(input.load_lines)))
162     z = np.empty((len(input.load_lines[1].load_nodes), len(input.load_lines)))
163     for i, load_line in enumerate(input.load_lines):
164         print(" Load Line", (i + 1))
165         for j, load_node in enumerate(load_line.load_nodes):
166             print(f" Node {j+1:3}", end="")
167             print(
168                 f" Position {load_node.position[0]:8.3f} {load_node.position[1]:8.3f} {load_node.position[2]:8.3f}",
169                 end="",
170             )
171             print(
172                 f" Distributed Force {load_node.distributed_force[0]:8.3f} {load_node.distributed_force[1]:8.3f} {load_node.distributed_force[2]:8.3f}",
173                 end=""
174             )

```

```

173     Fx[j, i] = float(load_node.distributed_force[0])
174     Fy[j, i] = float(load_node.distributed_force[1])
175     Fz[j, i] = float(load_node.distributed_force[2])
176     x[j, i] = float(load_node.position[0])
177     y[j, i] = float(load_node.position[1])
178     z[j, i] = float(load_node.position[2])
179
180 dp_x = np.empty((len(input.load_lines[1].load_nodes), len(input.load_lines)))
181 dp_y = np.empty((len(input.load_lines[1].load_nodes), len(input.load_lines)))
182 dp_z = np.empty((len(input.load_lines[1].load_nodes), len(input.load_lines)))
183 rr = np.sqrt(x**2 + y**2)
184 for i in range(len(input.load_lines)):
185     dp_x = -Fx[:, i] * N_AZIMUTH_AERO/ (2 * np.pi * rr[:, i] * R)
186     dp_y = -Fy[:, i] * N_AZIMUTH_AERO/ (2 * np.pi * rr[:, i] * R)
187     dp_z = -Fz[:, i] * N_AZIMUTH_AERO/ (2 * np.pi * rr[:, i] * R)
188
189 xv = x.flatten('F')
190 yv = y.flatten('F')
191 zv = z.flatten('F')
192 dpx = dp_x.flatten('F') / H
193 dpy = dp_y.flatten('F') / H
194 dpz = dp_z.flatten('F') / H
195 OUT_NAME = f'HOVER_test{time_step}'
196 with open(f'/archive/elicotteri_aerodinamica_share/Multixscale_A_F/fluent_copy/HOVER_test/dpx_{OUT_NAME}.prof', 'w') as fd:
197     fd.write(f'({dpx_{OUT_NAME}} point {len(xv)})\n')
198     fd.write('x\n')
199     fd.write('\n'.join(map(str, xv)))
200     fd.write('\n')
201     fd.write('y\n')
202     fd.write('\n'.join(map(str, yv)))
203     fd.write('\n')
204     fd.write('z\n')
205     fd.write('\n'.join(map(str, zv)))
206     fd.write('\n')
207     fd.write('dpx\n')
208     fd.write('\n'.join(map(str, dpx)))
209     fd.write('\n')
210
211 with open(f'/archive/elicotteri_aerodinamica_share/Multixscale_A_F/fluent_copy/HOVER_test/dpy_{OUT_NAME}.prof', 'w') as fd:
212     fd.write(f'({dpy_{OUT_NAME}} point {len(xv)})\n')
213     fd.write('x\n')
214     fd.write('\n'.join(map(str, xv)))
215     fd.write('\n')
216     fd.write('y\n')
217     fd.write('\n'.join(map(str, yv)))
218     fd.write('\n')
219     fd.write('z\n')
220     fd.write('\n'.join(map(str, zv)))
221     fd.write('\n')
222     fd.write('dpy\n')
223     fd.write('\n'.join(map(str, dpy)))
224     fd.write('\n')
225
226 with open(f'/archive/elicotteri_aerodinamica_share/Multixscale_A_F/fluent_copy/HOVER_test/dpz_{OUT_NAME}.prof', 'w') as fd:
227     fd.write(f'({dpz_{OUT_NAME}} point {len(xv)})\n')
228     fd.write('x\n')
229     fd.write('\n'.join(map(str, xv)))
230     fd.write('\n')
231     fd.write('y\n')
232     fd.write('\n'.join(map(str, yv)))
233     fd.write('\n')
234     fd.write('z\n')
235     fd.write('\n'.join(map(str, zv)))
236     fd.write('\n')
237     fd.write('dpz\n')
238     fd.write('\n'.join(map(str, dpz)))
239     fd.write('\n')
240
241 solver.solution.calculation_activity.execute_commands.enable()
242 solver.setup.cell_zone_conditions.fluid["ad_prism"].source_terms.sources= True
243 #READ PROF FILE
244 solver.file.read_profile(file_name= f"/archive/elicotteri_aerodinamica_share/Multixscale_A_F/fluent_copy/HOVER_test/dpx_{OUT_NAME}.prof")

```

```

245 solver.file.read_profile(file_name= f"/archive/elicotteri_aerodinamica_share/Multixscale_A_F/fluent_copy/
HOVER_test/dpy_{OUT_NAME}.prof")
246 solver.file.read_profile(file_name= f"/archive/elicotteri_aerodinamica_share/Multixscale_A_F/fluent_copy/
HOVER_test/dpz_{OUT_NAME}.prof")
247 solver.setup.cell_zone_conditions.fluid["ad_prism"].source_terms = {
248 'source_terms': {
249     'x-momentum': [{'option': 'profile', 'profile_name': f'dpx_{OUT_NAME}', 'field_name': 'dpx'}],
250     'y-momentum': [{'option': 'profile', 'profile_name': f'dpy_{OUT_NAME}', 'field_name': 'dpy'}],
251     'z-momentum': [{'option': 'profile', 'profile_name': f'dpz_{OUT_NAME}', 'field_name': 'dpz'}]
252 }
253 }
254
255 solver.solution.run_calculation.calculate()
256
257 print(" Evaluation Points")
258 k=0
259 v_x = []
260 v_y = []
261 v_z = []
262 vx = np.array ([])
263 vy = np.array ([])
264 vz = np.array ([])
265 x_p = np.array ([])
266 y_p = np.array ([])
267 z_p = np.array ([])
268 for point in input.evaluation_points:
269     print(f" {point[0]:8.3f} {point[1]:8.3f} {point[2]:8.3f}")
270     x_p = float(point[0])
271     y_p = float(point[1])
272     z_p = float(point[2])
273     if time_step == 1 :
274         solver.results-surfaces.point_surface.create("p-"+ str(k))
275         solver.results-surfaces.point_surface = {
276 'p-'+ str(k) : {'name' : 'p-'+ str(k), 'point': [x_p, y_p, z_p], 'snap_method': 'off'}}
277         v_x = solver.field_data.get_scalar_field_data(field_name = 'x-velocity', surface_name = 'p-'+ str(k),
node_value = False, boundary_value = False)
278         v_y = solver.field_data.get_scalar_field_data(field_name = 'y-velocity', surface_name = 'p-'+ str(k),
node_value = False, boundary_value = False)
279         v_z = solver.field_data.get_scalar_field_data(field_name = 'z-velocity', surface_name = 'p-'+ str(k),
node_value = False, boundary_value = False)
280         vx = np.append(vx, v_x[0].scalar_data)
281         vy = np.append(vy, v_y[0].scalar_data)
282         vz = np.append(vz, v_z[0].scalar_data)
283         k+=1
284
285 print(vx, vy, vz)
286 velocities = (vx, vy, vz)
287 air_density = 1.23 * time_step
288 evaluation_data = [
289     fluent_communicator.EvaluationData(air_density, get_row(velocities, i))
290     for i in range(len(vx))
291 ]
292
293 fluent_communicator.SendSolverOutput(evaluation_data)
294
295
296 print("Shutting down...")

```

3.6 Fluent Coupling Numerical Setup - Hover Test Case

The test case employed for this methodology corresponds to the Langley rotor, consistent with the previous approaches. The rotor was analyzed under hover conditions with an imposed collective pitch angle, as outlined earlier. Simulations were performed across a range of collective pitch angles, as specified in Table 1.

Mesh Generation. The meshing process for the Fluent simulation begins with a disk surface mesh generated using CATIA. This surface mesh is imported into Fluent's meshing mode, with meters as the unit length. The disk geometry, initially centered at the origin, is then translated by 0.02 meters in the z-direction. This translation ensures that the resulting volume mesh maintains a symmetric configuration with respect to the xy-plane at $z=0$, where the center of each cell approximately resides.

From the translated surface mesh, a volume mesh is generated with a thickness of one layer, set at 0.04 meters. This volume mesh utilizes prismatic elements with a triangular base, ensuring precise alignment of the mesh layers relative to the defined plane. Pyramid elements are strategically employed to discretize the transition zone between the disk

and the fluid domain, promoting mesh quality and accuracy.

Figure 16: Rotor mesh

To enhance resolution along the flow direction and capture detailed flow dynamics, a cylindrical refinement region is introduced. Within this region, a hexcore meshing scheme is applied. This scheme optimizes computational efficiency by utilizing Cartesian cells in the core of the domain, while tetrahedral cells are employed near boundaries to accommodate complex geometries and flow conditions effectively.

Beyond the refinement region, the external computational domain is defined as a square area measuring 35x35 units. This configuration allows ample space for flow development and minimizes boundary effects, contributing to robust simulation results. The hexcore meshing scheme is also extended to the external domain to maintain computational efficiency and ensure accurate resolution of boundary layers.

Close to the rotor disk, a fine mesh with multiple layers of prismatic elements is implemented to resolve the boundary layer effectively. This step is crucial for accurately capturing aerodynamic forces and ensuring simulation fidelity. The final mesh consists of a total of 8 million cells.

Turbulence Modeling. To model the turbulence effects accurately, the k-omega SST (Shear Stress Transport) model was employed. The k-omega SST model is renowned for its robustness in predicting flow separation under adverse pressure gradients, which is a common occurrence in rotor aerodynamics. The SST formulation blends the advantages of the k-omega model in the near-wall region with the k-epsilon model in the free stream, thereby providing a reliable prediction of both the boundary layer behavior and the wake flow.

The choice of the k-omega SST model was driven by its ability to handle the complex flow features around the rotor blades, including turbulent eddies, vortex shedding, and flow reattachment. This model's enhanced prediction capabilities make it well-suited for simulations involving rotating machinery where accurate depiction of flow separation and turbulence is critical.

Operating & Boundary Conditions. The operating conditions were set with gravity effects disabled, focusing solely on the aerodynamic forces. The operating pressure was set to standard atmospheric pressure (101325 Pa), and the reference pressure location was defined to ensure accurate pressure field computation. A pressure inlet and a pressure outlet were defined with specific turbulence parameters. The inlet was specified with a gauge total pressure that accounts for a velocity of 0.5 m/s, while the turbulence intensity and length scales were set using the K and Omega parameters. This configuration ensures that the initial inflow considers the rotor as already spinning.

Source Terms. Source terms were incorporated to model additional forces acting within the fluid domain. These terms were read from external profile files and applied to specific zones within the mesh. By specifying source terms for x-momentum, y-momentum, and z-momentum, the simulation can account for localized forces that affect the flow behavior. This approach is particularly useful for simulating effects such as rotor thrust and torque.

Figure 17: Local x momentum [Pa/m]

Figure 18: Local y momentum [Pa/m]

Figure 19: Local z momentum [Pa/m]

Solution Methods and Controls. In the steady state simulation the gradient scheme was set to the Green-Gauss node-based method, which provides a high degree of accuracy in gradient calculations. The coupled solver scheme was employed for pressure-velocity coupling, which enhances the stability and convergence rate of the simulation.

Relaxation factors and limiters were defined to control the numerical stability and prevent unphysical values. The use of advanced multi-grid methods for solving the pressure and temperature equations further improved the efficiency of the simulation by accelerating the convergence of the solution.

For the Fluent unsteady simulation a node-based Green-Gauss gradient reconstruction scheme was employed for

calculating gradients within the computational domain. The warped face gradient correction was disabled, as its effect on the solution accuracy was deemed negligible in this context.

An unsteady, first-order time-implicit solver was chosen to handle the transient nature of the rotor flowfield. The PISO (Pressure-Implicit with Splitting of Operators) scheme was adopted for pressure-velocity coupling, offering robust convergence for unsteady flows. The time step size was calculated dynamically based on the azimuthal resolution of the rotor, imposed by the mid fidelity aerodynamic module of Leonardo Aeromechanical Solver previous simulation, and the rotor's angular velocity (Ω), ensuring sufficient temporal resolution to capture rotor wake interactions accurately.

The simulation employed fixed time-stepping with a user-specified method, ensuring consistent time intervals for data exchange between Fluent and the external aerodynamic solver. Key parameters, such as the reporting interval and profile update frequency, were configured to provide detailed insights into the transient evolution of the flowfield.

Initialization and Iterative Solving. Hybrid initialization was used to initialize the flow field, providing a balanced starting point for the iterative solver. This method combines features of both standard and full multi-grid initialization, ensuring that the initial guess is sufficiently accurate to facilitate rapid convergence.

The steady state simulation was run in multiple stages, with progressively increasing the Courant number to balance accuracy and computational efficiency. This staged approach ensures that the solver adapts to the flow characteristics gradually, avoiding potential numerical instabilities.

Data Averaging and Output. To ensure statistically steady results, data sampling and field averaging were performed over a specified number of iterations. This process helps in capturing the mean flow characteristics by averaging out the transient fluctuations. The final averaged results were then extracted and saved to a binary file for post-processing.

This comprehensive approach to data averaging ensures that the results are not only accurate but also representative of the true flow behavior, providing valuable insights into the aerodynamic performance of the Langley rotor.

Specifically, the solver computed averages for quantities such as velocity components (mean-x-velocity, mean-y-velocity, mean-z-velocity) and turbulence parameters over each selected surface. Output points were chosen based on their significance in capturing detailed flow information near the Langley rotor. The points were distributed radially with around the rotor, covering azimuthal angles and radial distances.

Radial sections	Azimuthal angles
30	60°

Table 3: Number of radial sections and corresponding azimuthal angle intervals defining the sampling resolution on the disk.

Figure 20: Output points

The output points were carefully chosen to align with the rotor's geometry and operational conditions, ensuring that the collected data accurately represented the flow characteristics encountered by the rotor blades. For each selected output point, the solver generated output data which will be used as input for the mid-fidelity aerodynamic module of Leonardo Aeromechanical Solver.

Tip Correction After analyzing the results of the mid-fidelity aerodynamic simulation (Figure 25) with inflow data provided by Fluent, it was deemed necessary to implement a correction for the velocity distribution at the blade tip

(Figure 23). The aerodynamics of the rotor blade tip region are inherently complex due to various phenomena, including the formation of tip vortex wakes and their influence on the surface pressure and lift distribution along the blade. One significant effect in this region is the reduction in lifting capability, commonly referred to as *tip loss* [11].

The tip vortex forms as high-pressure air from the lower surface of the blade rolls over to the low-pressure region on the upper surface near the tip, generating a concentrated vortex structure. This vortex interacts with the flow field around the blade, inducing downwash and reducing the effective angle of attack. Consequently, the lift generated near the blade tip is diminished, which is a key factor not fully captured in simplified models such as Blade Element Theory (BET).

In the CFD simulation performed using Fluent, the uRANS model inherently accounts for the induced velocity effects resulting from the interaction of the blade with the wake. This includes the detailed calculation of the induced angle of attack (the angle between the relative velocity and the blade chord line), which reflects both the aerodynamic interaction with the rotor wake and the influence of the tip vortex. In contrast, the BET-based solver in the mid-fidelity aerodynamic module of Leonardo Aeromechanical Solver, when coupled with inflow data from Fluent, lacks a direct representation of the wake-induced velocity field. As a result, the induced angle of attack at the blade tip is not accurately captured, leading to discrepancies in the predicted loads and aerodynamic performance.

To address this limitation, a correction was introduced to reshape the velocity distribution at the blade tip. Alternatively, this issue could have been addressed by incorporating a tip loss factor in the subsequent mid-fidelity aerodynamic simulation within the coupling loop.

In the adopted solution, the inflow angle—defined as the sum of the induced inflow angle and the geometric pitch angle of the blade section—was recalculated. For a rotor blade, the inflow angle defines the effective angle of attack, which determines the aerodynamic loading on the blade. At the blade tip, the total inflow angle was adjusted to correspond to the condition where the section's lift coefficient equals zero, following principles derived from lifting line theory and blade element theory.

This correction process begins by referencing the airfoil performance tables to identify the effective angle of attack at which the lift coefficient becomes zero. Using this effective angle of attack and the known geometric pitch angle, the induced inflow angle was derived. From this induced inflow angle, the corresponding induced velocities were computed. The relationship governing the induced inflow angle is given by:

$$\alpha_{\text{induced}} = \arctan\left(\frac{V_z}{V_x}\right),$$

where V_z represents the axial (normal to the rotor disk) velocity component, including the effects of wake-induced flow, and V_x denotes the tangential velocity component (parallel to the rotor plane), combining both rotational and induced contributions.

To ensure a smooth spanwise velocity distribution, the correction interpolates between the maximum velocity value along the span and the recalculated value at the blade tip using a fourth-degree polynomial. This method was chosen because it provides a smooth transition while better preserving the integral aerodynamic loads across the blade span, maintaining consistency with the overall rotor aerodynamic performance. The comparison of the induced velocity distributions across the three sequential simulations, after the correction, is presented in Figure 24.

By applying this correction, the adjusted velocity distribution more accurately captures the aerodynamic behavior near the blade tip. This refinement compensates for the limitations of the Blade Element Theory (BET) model in representing wake-induced effects, thereby aligning the results more closely with those obtained from CFD simulations.

3.6.1 Results

In the following section, the results of the simulation are presented through contour plots of the V_z -component of velocity and static pressure, both visualized on a scan plane at $x = 0$.

The results of the Fluent simulation are visualized using contour plots of the V_z -component of velocity and static pressure on a scan plane at $x = 0$, providing insights into the flow field generated by the rotor.

Figure 21: Component Z Velocity contours (y-z plane at x=0) at collective 6.7°

Figure 22: Static Pressure contours (y-z plane at x=0) at collective 6.7°

3.6.2 Correction Comparison

The correction applied to the inflow at the blade tip addresses the discrepancies arising from the coupling of the momentum source theory (applied in Fluent) with the Blade Element Theory (BET) model used in the mid fidelity aerodynamic module of Leonardo Aeromechanical Solver. Without this correction, the simulation fails to replicate the behavior predicted by lifting line theory, particularly at the blade tip.

The first set of images (Figure 23) illustrates the induced velocity distribution on the two rotor blades as radial functions, respectively at 0° and 180° azimuth angles, based on the converged solution at the last rotor revolution.

Three simulation scenarios are compared:

1. Simulation conducted by the Mid-Fidelity Aerodynamic Module of Leonardo's Aeromechanical Solver with wake enabled, following lifting line theory (Figure 15: *Initialization-Compute Blade Loads()*).
2. Fluent simulation with momentum source theory applied (Figure 15: *Loop-uRANS()*).
3. Simulation conducted by the Mid-Fidelity Aerodynamic Module of Leonardo's Aeromechanical Solver with Fluent-provided inflow, simple BET model (Figure 15: *Loop-Compute Blade Loads()*).

The comparison highlights significant deviations between the induced velocity distributions of the three methods. The simulation conducted by the mid-fidelity aerodynamic module of Leonardo's Aeromechanical Solver with the wake enabled (first plot) aligns well with lifting line theory. In contrast, the coupling between Fluent and the mid-fidelity aerodynamic solver without correction (third plot) fails to adequately capture the expected tip losses as predicted by the mid-fidelity aerodynamic solver. While the inflow representation coming from Fluent appears accurate, showing a gradual increase in induced velocities toward the mid-span and a reduction near the tip due to vortex-induced downwash, the induced velocity distribution from the mid-fidelity aerodynamic solver exhibits an unrealistic trend that results in an inaccurate induced inflow angle and corresponding deviations in the lift coefficient.

Figure 23: Comparison of induced velocities

The second set of images demonstrates the induced velocity distribution after applying the correction to the Fluent-provided inflow. This correction ensures that the induction near the blade tip matches the expected downwash intensity caused by the tip vortex. The corrected inflow results in a radial distribution consistent with the simulation conducted by the mid-fidelity aerodynamic module of Leonardo's Aeromechanical Solver with the wake enabled.

The comparison shows a marked improvement in the agreement between the three methods. The correction ensures a coherent inflow distribution across all simulations, aligning with theoretical expectations. Moreover, the integral loads are conserved, confirming the validity of the corrected inflow.

Figure 24: Comparison of induced velocities with applied tip loss corrections.

Figure 25 illustrates the sectional loads distribution along the blade span, comparing the corrected and uncorrected inflow results. The corrected inflow (red curve) exhibits the expected behavior, with a peak in loads shortly after the mid-span position and a gradual reduction toward the tip due to tip losses. This behavior is consistent with the results from the simulation conducted by the mid-fidelity aerodynamic solver with the wake enabled. Conversely, the uncorrected inflow fails to capture the characteristic load trends, particularly near the blade tip.

These results emphasize the importance of correcting the inflow in simulations where the wake model is disabled. By addressing the discrepancies between the momentum source theory and the BET model, the correction ensures a realistic representation of the blade aerodynamics, accurately capturing the effects of induced inflow and tip losses.

Figure 25: Loads correction comparison

4 Comparison

In this section, the implemented methodologies are compared using the hover test case with externally imposed motion, under the conditions outlined in Section 1. Results are presented for the figure of merit as function of the ratio C_T/σ , as well as for thrust coefficient and power coefficient as functions of collective pitch. Additionally, the computational time required by each CFD methodology discussed in this report is provided, with reference to the time needed for approximately 1000 iterations in Fluent, which was typically required to achieve convergence in most of the simulations conducted.

Figure 26: Thrust coefficient (C_T) vs. collective pitch angle comparison for all simulation methods under hover conditions.

Figure 27: Power coefficient (C_P) vs. collective pitch angle comparison for all simulation methods under hover conditions.

Figure 28: Figure of Merit (FM) as a function of the thrust-to-solidity ratio, comparing all simulation methods under hover conditions.

Figure 29: Comparison of Computational Times for Analyzed CFD Methodologies

For this specific test case, the Virtual Blade Model (VBM) demonstrates the highest efficiency and accuracy among the evaluated methods, as evidenced by the Figures 26 27 28. In particular, the distribution of the thrust coefficient and other relevant parameters closely matches the experimental data. However, due to its inherent limitations, VBM cannot be used as the CFD component in the coupling framework targeted in this study.

In contrast, the 3D Multiple Reference Frame (MRF) approach, although theoretically well-suited for integration with an aeromechanical solver, displayed reduced accuracy in these simulations. This is especially evident when examining the power coefficient distribution, Figure 27, and the figure of merit, in Figure 28, both of which deviate more significantly from the experimental data. This behavior could be attributed to a not fine enough computational grid, to the approximation of steady-state flow, and to the turbulence modeling approximation. With a finer mesh, accuracy could have been improved, albeit at a substantial increase in computational expense, which would further reduce the feasibility of a dynamic coupling. Alternatively, adopting a sliding mesh technique in an unsteady simulation would likely enhance accuracy but with an even greater computational burden. In addition, varying the extent of the MRF volume adopted to represent the rotating frame may have an impact on results.

The primary goal of these tests was not to achieve precise quantitative results but to establish a benchmark for analyzing the trade-offs between computational demand and accuracy. The accuracy of the 3D MRF methodology is well-documented and validated in various contexts beyond the scope of this study, supporting its suitability for rotorcraft applications.

Considering the computational time required for the compared CFD methods (Figure 29), the dual-solver approach employing *Fluent Coupling* stands out among the two methodologies suitable for integration with an aeromechanical solver. This approach demonstrated superior convenience and flexibility, offering seamless compatibility with external tools.

The results of this study revealed numerical discrepancies, as evident from the behavior of the thrust coefficient in Figure 26. In particular, the slope does not align with the experimental data, leading to significant deviations at both very low and high collective pitch values. This behavior arises from the coupling of two distinct theoretical frameworks—Blade Element Theory (BET) and Momentum Theory (MT). While BET provides a high-fidelity representation of aerodynamic forces by considering local blade sections, MT, used in the momentum model, simplifies the flow

interaction, which can lead to inaccuracies, especially at extreme operating conditions. These discrepancies were mitigated to some extent by implementing a velocity correction at the blade tip, as detailed in Section 3.6.2. However, further improvements could be achieved by introducing a tip loss factor in the mid fidelity aerodynamic module of Leonardo Aeromechanical Solver portion of the coupling, which would better account for the local flow effects at the blade tip, especially at high collective pitches.

Looking at the power coefficient distribution in Figure 27, the behavior is generally reasonable, with notable discrepancies occurring only at very high collective pitch values. This suggests that while the method accurately captures rotor performance for a wide range of operating conditions, some adjustments are needed to improve accuracy at higher collective angles, where flow separation and stall effects become more pronounced.

The Figure of Merit (FoM) distribution, as shown in Figure 28, demonstrates a more favorable comparison to experimental data, outperforming the 3D-MRF approach. Although not a perfect match, the results remain relatively close to experimental values, indicating that the method is reliable for assessing rotor performance across a range of flight conditions.

Despite these numerical uncertainties, they remain within acceptable limits, especially when weighed against the significant advantages provided by this method. These advantages include enhanced adaptability, a substantial reduction in computational costs, and the ability to incorporate complex flow phenomena that are beyond the reach of simplified methods. Notably, this method enables the study of interactions between multiple rotors and rotorcraft operating in intricate environments, such as shipboard scenarios.

Such advanced cases, which involve wake interactions and detailed blade-resolved computations, are currently impractical using standalone CFD due to prohibitive computational demands. By validating the dual-solver framework through these simulations, this study paves the way for expanding the capabilities of computational methods. It enables efficient and accurate analyses of complex rotorcraft dynamics while effectively managing computational resources.

5 Conclusions and outlook

In this report we have discussed the activities carried out to couple the LB software waLBerla and the commercial Finite Volume solver Fluent with a Leonardo's proprietary aeromechanical solver.

As concerns the LB solver, this coupling has been necessary to implement an ASA method for describing the aerodynamics of rotating blades with a good compromise between physical accuracy and computational load. We point out that this approach is very flexible as it is totally blind to the details of the adopted collision model and the chosen velocity discretization for the particle distributions. This is extremely relevant as it can be directly adopted in conjunction with advanced collision methods (as for example the Onsager-Regularized (OReg) approach discussed in Ref. [12]) which are expected to provide increased stability for large Mach-number conditions as those experience near the rotor tips. In this regards, the usage of the OReg approach (or other alternative regularization procedures) within this framework is straightforward and only require an appropriate inclusion of forces in the regularization step.

The chosen implementation procedure is already open for future coupling with a full aero-mechanical of the rotor blades as the computed blade forces can be taken as input for a structural solver describing the mechanical response of the blades. As already mentioned, this will be the main focus for the remaining part of the project. Finally, we also point out that the present implementation, even without a full description of the blade's mechanical response to aerodynamic external forces, can be adopted to model the rotor's wake near complex solid surfaces (as ship or buildings) in various wind conditions and achieve an accurate description of dangerous helicopter's landing operations.

As concerns the FV coupling, a benchmark was established to analyze the trade-offs between computational demand and accuracy, with different CFD methodologies evaluated for their feasibility in coupling with a structural dynamics solver. Computational cost was the primary criterion.

The analyses revealed that simplified methods are essential to ensure computational efficiency while supporting external tool integration. An unsteady actuator disk-based simplification coupled with the mid-fidelity aerodynamic module of Leonardo Aeromechanical Solver was adopted, allowing accurate wake structure modeling without the high computational costs of single-solver unsteady Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (uRANS) methods. This approach strikes a balance between efficiency and physical accuracy, ensuring seamless integration into a unified aero-structural simulation framework.

While numerical uncertainties were observed, they remain within acceptable limits, especially when weighed against the method's significant advantages. These include enhanced adaptability, reduced computational costs, and the ability to model complex flow phenomena beyond the reach of simplified methods. In particular, this methodology, as the implementation of LB, allows the analysis of the rotor's wake near complex solid surfaces (such as ships or buildings) in various wind conditions and achieves an accurate description of dangerous helicopter landing operations.

Advanced cases involving wake interactions and detailed blade-resolved computations are currently infeasible with standalone CFD due to prohibitive computational demands. By validating the dual-solver framework through these simulations, this study establishes a robust foundation for efficient and accurate analysis of complex rotorcraft dynamics while effectively managing computational resources.

References

Acronyms used

CFD Computational Fluid Dynamics

Software mentioned

waLBerla Widely Applicable Lattice Boltzmann solver from ERLAngen

URLs referenced

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